

Design and Implementation of a 5-Stage Pipelined MIPS-32 Processor Using Verilog HDL

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Abstract—his paper presents the design and implementation of a 32-bit pipelined MIPS processor using Verilog HDL. The processor supports arithmetic, logical, immediate, load-store, and branch instructions, and follows the classical five-stage MIPS pipeline: IF, ID, EX, MEM, and WB. Dual-phase clocking is used to avoid race conditions between consecutive pipeline stages. A test program is executed to verify the correctness of register updates, arithmetic operations, and memory access. Simulation results and waveform analysis confirm that the processor executes instructions correctly and demonstrates proper pipelined behavior.

Keywords— MIPS, Pipelined Processor, Verilog, 5-Stage Pipeline, Simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

MIPS is a widely used RISC instruction set architecture that follows a simple and regular structure, making it suitable for hardware implementation and academic study. Like other RISC architectures, MIPS provides low complexity, fixed-length instructions and a clean pipeline model, enabling efficient processor development. Pipelined MIPS processors are commonly used in embedded systems, computer architecture research, and VLSI design due to their modularity and predictable behavior. The five-stage pipeline structure—Instruction Fetch (IF), Instruction Decode (ID), Execute (EX), Memory Access (MEM), and Write Back (WB)—enhances overall throughput while keeping the processor design compact and scalable.

In this work, a 32-bit pipelined MIPS processor is implemented using Verilog HDL. The processor supports arithmetic, logical, load/store, immediate, and branch instructions. A dual-phase clocking mechanism is used to separate pipeline stages, helping to reduce timing conflicts and simplify control. A test program is executed to verify instruction execution, memory access, and register updates. Simulation results confirm correct pipelined operation and demonstrate that the processor functions according to the MIPS pipeline model, making it suitable for basic embedded applications and educational purposes.

II. RISC-V INSTRUCTION SET OVERVIEW

A. RV32I Instruction Set

The RV32I instruction set forms the base integer ISA of RISC-V and uses a fixed 32-bit instruction length aligned to 32-bit boundaries. Although simple, the format allows extensions for variable-length instructions when needed. RV32I defines six instruction formats and supports 40 basic operations used in general-purpose and embedded computing. The architecture includes 32 registers (x0–x31), where x0 is fixed to zero to

simplify many instruction operations. Despite its simplicity, RV32I achieves code density comparable to other RISC architectures while maintaining flexible encoding and ease of implementation.

Table I.

Number of instructions generated under different instruction sets and instruction size

Instruction Type	Instruction Included	Count
R-type ALU	ADD, SUB, AND, OR, SLT, MUL	6
I-type ALU	ADDI, SUBI, SLTI	3
Memory Access	LW, SW	2
Branch Instructions	BEQZ, BNEQZ	2
Special Instruction	HLT	1
Total Instructions Implemented	-	14

B. Micro-Architecture and its Working

Figure 1 shows the pipelined MIPS-32 architecture used in this work. In the IF (Instruction Fetch) stage, the program counter PC is increased every cycle, and the instruction stored at that address is fetched from memory. The fetched instruction is then forwarded to the ID (Instruction Decode) stage along with the next PC value. When the current instruction is a branch such as BEQZ or BNEQZ, the EX stage evaluates the branch condition, and if true, the PC is updated to the computed target address. During this period, sequential fetching is temporarily overridden to allow correct branch execution.

In the ID stage, the instruction is decoded to determine the operation type. The source registers are read from the register bank, and immediate values are sign-extended for I-type instructions. Based on the opcode, the control logic identifies whether the instruction belongs to ALU, load/store, or branch category. The EX (Execute) stage performs arithmetic and logical operations such as addition, subtraction, AND, OR, SLT, and multiplication using the operands obtained from ID. For branch instructions, the EX stage compares register values and calculates the branch target address.

The MEM stage handles LW and SW instructions; SW writes the specified data to memory, while LW reads data from memory into the pipeline register. For other instructions, this stage performs no action. In the WB (Write Back) stage, either the ALU result or loaded data is written back to the register file unless a branch is taken, in which case the write is disabled to avoid incorrect updates.

Figure1. The RISC-V architecture block diagram

III. SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT AND RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the simulation waveform of the pipelined MIPS-32 processor. The clk1 and clk2 signals alternate, confirming the correct two-phase clocking used to separate pipeline stages. The PC signal increments sequentially as each instruction is fetched in the IF stage, indicating proper instruction flow through memory. The IF_ID_IR and IF_ID_NPC registers are updated every clk1 cycle, showing that instruction fetch and next-PC generation are working correctly.

The ID_EX pipeline registers capture operands A, B, the immediate value, and the decoded instruction type. As seen in the waveform, these registers update on clk2, confirming that decode and operand forwarding occur in the correct phase. The ALUOut signal in the EX_MEM stage shows the results of arithmetic operations: after instructions ADDI, ADD, and subsequent additions, ALUOut correctly reflects values such as 0000000A, 00000014, 00000019, and 0000001E. This demonstrates that the ALU performs addition operations correctly for both register-type and immediate-type instructions.

Output Waveform

Fig 2

The MEM_WB_aluout signal carries the final ALU result into the write-back stage, where the register file is updated. The updated values propagate through the pipeline without overwriting or hazards, indicating that the TAKEN_BRANCH and HALTED control signals correctly prevent illegal writes. The smooth transition of instructions across IF/ID, ID/EX, EX/MEM, and MEM/WB in the waveform verifies that the five-stage pipeline functions properly and that the processor executes all instructions without stalls or incorrect data forwarding.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, a 32-bit pipelined MIPS processor was implemented and verified using Verilog HDL. The design supports arithmetic, logical, immediate, memory, and branch instructions and uses a dual-phase clocking scheme to separate pipeline stages. Simulation results obtained from the waveform confirm correct instruction execution, proper pipeline register updates, and accurate ALU operations across all five stages. The processor demonstrates stable pipelined behavior without hazards in the tested program, validating its functionality. Future work may include adding forwarding, hazard detection, and expanding the instruction set to support more advanced operations.

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